

Interpretable Vision Transformers in Image Classification via SVDA

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ABSTRACT Vision Transformers (ViTs) have achieved state-of-the-art performance in image classification, yet their attention mechanisms often remain opaque and exhibit dense, non-structured behaviors. In this work, we adapt our previously proposed SVD-Inspired Attention (SVDA) mechanism to the ViT architecture, introducing a geometrically grounded formulation that enhances interpretability, sparsity, and spectral structure. We apply the use of interpretability indicators—originally proposed with SVDA—to monitor attention dynamics during training and assess structural properties of the learned representations. Experimental evaluations on four widely used benchmarks—CIFAR-10, FashionMNIST, CIFAR-100, and ImageNet-100—together with an additional pretrained fine-tuning study in a standard ViT setting show that SVDA preserves competitive classification behavior in our experimental settings while providing descriptive diagnostics of attention structure. In the pretrained setting, we integrate the exact SVDA operator into the late transformer blocks of a standard pretrained ViT and fine-tune on ImageNet-100, providing additional evidence that the proposed mechanism remains viable beyond compact from-scratch training. While the current framework offers descriptive insights rather than prescriptive guidance, our results establish SVDA as a comprehensive and informative tool for analyzing and developing structured attention models in computer vision. This work lays the foundation for future advances in explainable AI, spectral diagnostics, and attention-based model design.

INDEX TERMS Transformers, Self-Attention, Singular Value Decomposition, SVD, SVD-Inspired Attention, SVDA, Attention Mechanism, Deep Learning, Image Classification, Interpretability, Interpretable Machine Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Vision Transformers (ViTs) have demonstrated remarkable success in image classification tasks, often surpassing conventional convolutional architectures in various benchmarks [1]. However, despite their effectiveness, ViTs and other Transformer-based models face a persistent challenge: the lack of interpretability in their attention mechanisms. The standard self-attention formulation, based on dense dot-product interactions, often produces attention maps that are opaque and difficult to interpret. These patterns frequently lack spatial or semantic structure, limiting their utility in explaining model behavior. Prior work has shown that attention maps (when visualized) may not reliably reflect the reasoning behind predictions [2], and recent work has further examined the faithfulness of Vision Transformer explanations directly

in the visual domain [3]. Visualization alone often fails to provide actionable insight. The absence of semantically structured attention maps hinders both model interpretability across a wide range of tasks, from standard image classification benchmarks to high-stakes decision-making domains [4]. Addressing this gap requires attention mechanisms that go beyond surface-level visualizations to offer geometric regularity and semantically meaningful structure.

Motivation. The interpretability of attention patterns has emerged as a key concern in both academic and applied settings. Studies have shown that attention maps may not reliably align with the model's decision rationale [2], and popular visualization tools often fail to capture meaningful structure. In image classification, this undermines the potential for attention-based models to support tasks that re-

quire transparency, human oversight, or semantic reasoning. More broadly, in high-stakes domains such as healthcare, autonomous systems, and scientific discovery, reliance on black-box attention mechanisms poses ethical and practical risks [4]. *These concerns highlight the need for alternative formulations of attention that promote both transparency and structured behavior.*

Research Question. Can SVDA, embedded directly in ViT self-attention as an intrinsic (ante-hoc) interpretability mechanism, preserve competitive image-classification behavior on widely used benchmarks and in a standard pre-trained fine-tuning regime, while providing structural, descriptive indicators of attention?

Our Approach. To address this challenge, we propose the integration of our previously introduced SVD-inspired Attention (SVDA) mechanism [5] into the Vision Transformer architecture. SVDA replaces the standard dot-product attention with a geometrically structured formulation that decouples directional information from spectral significance. It applies soft-orthonormal projections to the query and key spaces, combined with a learned diagonal matrix Σ that modulates the attention interaction based on the spectral importance of each latent dimension. This structure induces attention maps that are more focused and spectrally structured, while keeping the overall ViT encoder architecture unchanged. In addition to improving attention structure, SVDA enables a set of descriptive indicators that quantify the internal dynamics of attention layers. These indicators offer a principled diagnostic framework for analyzing attention interpretability, alignment, and information concentration across layers and heads.

Scope and Contribution. This paper studies SVDA in two complementary regimes. First, we evaluate compact ViT-style models trained from scratch on four widely used image-classification datasets: CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, FashionMNIST, and ImageNet-100. Second, to strengthen validation in a more standard Transformer setting, we additionally study a pre-trained fine-tuning configuration in which the exact previously published SVDA operator is integrated into the late transformer blocks of a pre-trained ViT backbone and fine-tuned on ImageNet-100. Across these settings, SVDA preserves competitive classification behavior while the proposed indicators provide descriptive diagnostics of attention structure. Our key contributions are:

- The adaptation of SVDA to Vision Transformers, introducing geometric and spectral constraints for improved interpretability.
- A comparative evaluation on four standard benchmarks, showing that SVDA preserves competitive performance while enhancing attention structure.
- An additional validation study in a standard pre-trained/fine-tuned ViT regime, implemented through late-block integration of the exact SVDA operator into a pre-trained ViT backbone on ImageNet-100.
- The deployment of interpretability indicators as descriptive tools to assess internal attention dynamics, faithful-

ness, and structural behavior.

The results highlight the potential of SVDA as an interpretable and geometrically structured attention mechanism for image classification, bridging the gap between spectral theory and practical Transformer architectures. Our work introduces a principled framework for understanding and evaluating structured attention models, supported by spectral indicators that quantify interpretability and sparsity. These contributions lay the foundation for prescriptive attention design, where attention structures are explicitly optimized for transparency, and motivate further research in explainable AI, attention regularization, and spectral model compression.

II. RELATED WORK

Several recent efforts have focused on enhancing interpretability in Vision Transformers *by modifying how attention is visualized or trained*. For instance, Chefer et al. [6] proposed gradient-based relevance propagation to improve the faithfulness of attention explanations in ViTs. Similarly, ProtoViT [7] integrates prototype-based reasoning to support case-based explanations, enabling “this looks like that” interpretability. IA-ViT [8] modifies the training objective to encourage inherently interpretable attention heads. These approaches emphasize interpretability either post hoc or through auxiliary training objectives, but they do not structurally alter the attention mechanism itself.

In parallel, several approaches have explored the *injection of spectral and geometric structure* into attention mechanisms. Singularformer [9] learns a neural approximation of the SVD of the attention matrix, enabling linear-time computation while preserving global dependencies. Cosformer [10] replaces the dot-product kernel with cosine similarity to encourage directional alignment and improve efficiency. Primal-Attention [11] decomposes self-attention in the primal token space using a kernelized SVD formulation, enhancing representational capacity with theoretical guarantees. Recent work has also examined how explicitly controlling the spectral conditioning of attention layers impacts optimization and performance [12]. In a different direction, Transformer-VQ achieves dense softmax attention in linear time via vector-quantized keys and a caching mechanism, highlighting that operator-level redesigns can target distinct trade-offs beyond standard quadratic attention [13]. While each method introduces valuable structural priors, none provide a unified decomposition that explicitly separates directional and spectral contributions, nor do they furnish interpretable structural diagnostics for attention analysis.

Positioning and novelty. SVDA modifies the core similarity operator of self-attention by replacing dot-product scores with the SVD-inspired bilinear form $Q\Sigma K^T$, where Q and K are ℓ_2 -normalized and Σ is a learned diagonal spectral modulator per head [5]. This differs from approaches that improve Transformers by explicitly controlling the spectral conditioning of attention layers [12], which do not insert a learned diagonal spectral operator inside the query–key interaction. It also differs from Singularformer [9], which

targets linear-time computation via an SVD approximation of the attention matrix; in contrast, SVDA uses a lightweight diagonal spectral gate to decouple direction (from normalized Q, K) and spectral importance (from Σ). Primal-Attention [11] decomposes attention in the primal/token space via kernelized formulations, whereas SVDA performs head-wise modulation in the latent feature space through Σ . Finally, Cosformer [10] replaces dot-product with a cosine-style kernel primarily for efficiency; while SVDA likewise normalizes Q, K , its learned Σ introduces adaptive per-dimension spectral weighting that cannot be reduced to a fixed kernel substitution.

Architecturally, SVDA is not a post-hoc wrapper: it replaces the attention score computation inside each Transformer block while preserving the ViT encoder scaffold (patch embedding, [CLS] token, positional embeddings, and residual pathways). At the same time, SVDA can be viewed as a constrained reparameterization within the block (same input/output interfaces) whose new component is the explicit, learnable diagonal spectral operator Σ modulating normalized query–key interactions, enabling the indicator-based structural diagnostics used throughout this work.

Beyond structural modification, some works have aimed to *develop metrics that quantify attention behavior*. Abnar and Zuidema [14] proposed attention flow as a means to measure information propagation across layers, but their approach is not designed to capture structural clarity, sparsity, or interpretability in a principled way. Our work introduces six structural indicators—spectral entropy, effective rank, angular alignment, selectivity index, spectral sparsity, and perturbation robustness—that together provide a descriptive framework for analyzing attention dynamics. These metrics quantify focus, diversity, alignment, and stability at the head and layer level, enabling principled diagnostics of interpretability and structural behavior in Vision Transformers.

This paper builds on our prior work introducing SVDA [5], which provided a theoretical formulation of structured attention based on soft-orthonormal projections and spectral modulation. In the current study, we adapt this formulation to the Vision Transformer architecture and apply it to image classification tasks. Unlike earlier works that treat attention as a black-box or seek to interpret it only after training, SVDA embeds interpretability into the attention computation itself. Moreover, it enables principled structural diagnostics during training, providing a basis for prescriptive design of transparent, structured attention models in computer vision.

III. SVDA IN VISION TRANSFORMERS

In standard dot-product attention, similarity and magnitude are entangled: large-norm projections can dominate attention scores even when their directions are weakly aligned, which can encourage dense and harder-to-interpret attention patterns. SVDA separates these roles by enforcing geometric similarity through ℓ_2 -normalized Q and K (so interactions reflect cosine alignment), while a learned diagonal spectral modulator Σ explicitly controls the contribution of each

Algorithm 1 Integrating SVDA into a ViT Transformer block (per forward pass)

Require: token embeddings $X \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times N \times d}$, heads h , head dim $d_k = d/h$, weights W^Q, W^K, W^V, W^O , diagonal spectra $\Sigma_i = \text{diag}(\sigma_i)$

- 1: **for** $i = 1$ to h **do**
- 2: $Q_i \leftarrow XW_i^Q, K_i \leftarrow XW_i^K, V_i \leftarrow XW_i^V$ (linear projections)
- 3: $\hat{Q}_i \leftarrow \text{normalize}(Q_i), \hat{K}_i \leftarrow \text{normalize}(K_i)$ (row-wise ℓ_2)
- 4: $S_i \leftarrow \frac{(\hat{Q}_i \Sigma_i) \hat{K}_i^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ (SVDA scores)
- 5: $A_i \leftarrow \text{softmax}(S_i)$ (row-wise over keys)
- 6: $Z_i \leftarrow A_i V_i$ (head output)
- 7: **end for**
- 8: $Z \leftarrow \text{Concat}(Z_1, \dots, Z_h) W^O$ (multi-head output)
- 9: **return** Z

latent dimension. This makes the score formation easier to reason about—direction captures which tokens are related, and Σ captures which latent factors are emphasized—and it directly motivates the spectral/structural indicators used in our evaluation. This work investigates the empirical impact of integrating SVDA [5] into Vision Transformers (ViTs) for image classification. The core SVDA score computation is defined as:

$$S = \frac{(Q\Sigma)K^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}} \quad (1)$$

where $S \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ denotes the pre-softmax attention scores for a single head over N tokens (including [CLS]). Following [5], queries and keys are row-wise ℓ_2 -normalized, i.e., $Q = \text{normalize}(XW^Q) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d_k}$ and $K = \text{normalize}(XW^K) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d_k}$ are the row-wise ℓ_2 -normalized query/key projections of the token matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$ (single head shown), and $\Sigma = \text{diag}(\sigma) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_k \times d_k}$ is a learned diagonal spectral modulator. Softmax scaling and normalization are then applied row-wise over keys:

$$A = \text{softmax}(S), \quad (2)$$

$$Z = AV, \quad (3)$$

with $V = XW^V$. In the multi-head setting, each head i has its own $(Q_i, K_i, V_i, \Sigma_i)$ and produces $Z_i = A_i V_i$; the block output is $\text{Concat}(Z_1, \dots, Z_h) W^O$.

Integration procedure (pseudo-code). Algorithm 1 summarizes how SVDA replaces dot-product attention inside an otherwise standard ViT block, following the implementation used in our experiments.

Training-time additions. For SVDA runs, we augment the task loss with (i) an orthogonality regularizer on W^Q, W^K and (ii) a spectral-entropy regularizer on $\{\sigma_i\}$ (Sec. IV), while all other ViT components (patch embedding, [CLS], positional embeddings, residual pathways) remain unchanged.

FIGURE 1. Attention schematic: (a) standard scaled dot-product [15], (b) SVDA with diagonal modulation $Q\Sigma$ [5].

To ensure a direct comparison with the standard ViT architecture [1], our implementation follows the original embedding pipeline: each input image is divided into non-overlapping patches of size $P \times P$, which are flattened into vectors and passed through a learned linear projection to produce patch embeddings. A learnable [CLS] token is prepended, and fixed-length learnable positional embeddings are added to retain spatial order. The resulting token sequence is then processed by a Transformer encoder. The only deviation from the original ViT baseline is the replacement of the self-attention score computation with SVDA, as defined in Eq. 1 and detailed in [5]. This is an architectural change at the level of the attention operator (the similarity/kernel used inside the block), while the surrounding encoder scaffold and the block input/output interfaces remain unchanged. FIGURE 1 summarizes the SVDA modification relative to standard attention.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. DATASETS AND PREPROCESSING

We conducted experiments on four image classification benchmarks of increasing complexity: FashionMNIST, CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and ImageNet-100. Each dataset is processed using standard training/test splits and minimal preprocessing:

- FashionMNIST: 28×28 grayscale images of clothing items across 10 classes. We use only tensor conversion (no augmentation).
- CIFAR-10 / CIFAR-100: 32×32 RGB images from 10/100 classes. Augmentations include random cropping (padding=4), horizontal flipping, and random rotation within $\pm 15^\circ$.
- ImageNet-100: A curated 100-class subset of ImageNet-1K, with images resized to 224×224 , using bicubic interpolation, and augmented with horizontal flipping.
- No additional regularization (e.g., MixUp, CutMix) or heavy augmentation is applied, to keep the training protocol intentionally simple and isolate the architectural contribution of SVDA without confounding effects. This design choice prioritizes a clean comparison of attention mechanisms and the proposed indicators

over maximizing absolute accuracy.

We do not apply normalization in the input pipeline (i.e., no mean/std normalization) in order to keep the preprocessing consistent and minimal across datasets. Each image is divided into non-overlapping square patches. These patches are flattened and passed through a learned linear projection layer to produce fixed-length embeddings. Learnable positional encodings are added to the embedded sequence before input to the Transformer encoder.

B. MODEL ARCHITECTURE

We use compact ViT-style encoders (custom configurations, not standard ViT-Base/ViT-Large), with architectural parameters scaled according to input resolution. For FashionMNIST, CIFAR-10, and CIFAR-100, the model uses an embedding dimension of 256, 4 Transformer layers, 4 attention heads per layer, an MLP hidden dimension of 1024, and a patch size of 4×4 . For ImageNet-100, the configuration is adjusted to an embedding dimension of 96, 8 layers, 2 attention heads, an MLP hidden dimension of 384, and a patch size of 8×8 .

A learnable [CLS] token is prepended to the patch sequence before being passed into the Transformer encoder. Each Transformer block applies Layer Normalization prior to both the self-attention mechanism and the feedforward sublayer. GELU is used as the activation function in all feedforward networks.

C. TRAINING AND OPTIMIZATION

For the compact from-scratch setting, all models are trained for 100 epochs in PyTorch. We use Adam with default parameters, no weight decay, and no learning-rate scheduling; early stopping is disabled. A learning rate of 3×10^{-4} is used for FashionMNIST, CIFAR-10, and CIFAR-100, and 1×10^{-4} for ImageNet-100. The batch size is set to 64 for all datasets except ImageNet-100, which uses a batch size of 32. Cross-entropy loss is used throughout. The main body of our evaluation focuses on compact ViT-style models trained from scratch in order to isolate the architectural effect of replacing dot-product attention with SVDA. For SVDA, two lightweight regularization terms are applied:

- Orthogonality regularization on the query/key projection matrices with weight $\lambda_{\text{ortho}} = 10^{-3}$ for FashionMNIST/CIFAR-10/CIFAR-100 and $\lambda_{\text{ortho}} = 3 \times 10^{-4}$ for ImageNet-100, to promote soft orthonormality.
- Spectral-entropy regularization on Σ with weight $\lambda_{\text{ent}} = 10^{-3}$, encouraging concentration in the learned spectrum.

While the proposed indicator family is primarily used in this work as a descriptive diagnostic framework, the spectral-entropy term introduces a lightweight prescriptive component at training time by explicitly encouraging concentration in the learned SVDA spectrum.

To broaden the empirical scope beyond compact from-scratch training, we additionally evaluate SVDA in a pre-

trained fine-tuning setting based on a ViT-Tiny backbone (vit_tiny_patch16_224) pretrained on ImageNet-1K. In this setting, we compare: (i) a baseline pretrained ViT-Tiny fine-tuned on ImageNet-100, and (ii) an SVDA variant in which the exact SVDA operator replaces the attention computation only in the last two transformer blocks, while the earlier pretrained blocks remain unchanged. This late-block integration was adopted to preserve the learned low- and mid-level pretrained representation geometry while testing whether SVDA remains viable in a standard pretrained/fine-tuned ViT regime. Both models use the same pretrained backbone family, the same ImageNet-100 data split, and the same fine-tuning protocol. For this pretrained setting, we fine-tune for 20 epochs using AdamW with learning rate 2×10^{-5} , weight decay 10^{-4} , batch size 8, and the same ImageNet-100 train/validation split used in the from-scratch experiments.

The SVDA theory analysis [5] provides mechanism-level motivation for why the SVDA operator induces measurable geometric and spectral structure and why the proposed indicators are meaningful diagnostics of that structure. We therefore adopt matched deterministic protocols within each regime to isolate the architectural effect of replacing dot-product attention with SVDA under otherwise comparable training setups.

D. EVALUATION METRICS AND LOGGING

Beyond classification accuracy and training times, we evaluate the interpretability and structure of attention using the six interpretability indicators introduced in [5]:

- Spectral Entropy and Effective Rank to measure spectral complexity.
- Spectral Sparsity to show the proportion of negligible spectral weights in Σ .
- Angular Alignment as the average cosine similarity between normalized queries and keys.
- Selectivity Index as the degree of attention concentration across tokens.
- Perturbation Robustness as an index of change in attention maps under additive input noise.

Implementation of SVDA indicators. We use the six SVDA indicators defined in [5] as canonical measures of attention structure, and compute them from internal SVDA quantities per layer and per head at each epoch. Let $A \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ be the post-softmax attention matrix of a head, and let $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{d_k}$ denote the diagonal entries of Σ for that head. We form a normalized spectrum $p_i = \sigma_i^2 / (\sum_j \sigma_j^2 + \varepsilon)$ with $\varepsilon = 10^{-8}$.

- **Spectral Entropy:** $H(\Sigma) = -\sum_i p_i \log(p_i + \varepsilon)$ (unitless; $H \in [0, \log d_k]$, lower \Rightarrow more concentrated spectrum).
- **Effective Rank:** $r_{\text{eff}}(\Sigma) = \exp(H(\Sigma))$ (unitless; $r_{\text{eff}} \in [1, d_k]$, lower \Rightarrow fewer effective spectral degrees of freedom).

- **Spectral Sparsity:** $s(\Sigma) = \frac{1}{d_k} \sum_i \mathbb{I}(|\sigma_i| < \tau)$ with $\tau = 10^{-3}$ (unitless; $s \in [0, 1]$, higher \Rightarrow more near-zero spectral entries).
- **Angular Alignment:** following [5], the canonical quantity is $\cos \theta_{ij} = \langle \hat{q}_i, \hat{k}_j \rangle$ for query-key pairs (i, j) ; in our implementation, we log the diagonal proxy $\alpha_{\text{diag}} = \mathbb{E}_{b,n} \left[\langle \hat{q}_{b,n}, \hat{k}_{b,n} \rangle \right]$ (unitless; $\alpha_{\text{diag}} \in [-1, 1]$, higher \Rightarrow stronger cosine alignment at matching token indices).
- **Selectivity Index:** for each query row i , $\text{sel}(A_i) = 1 - \frac{\sum_j A_{ij}^2}{(\sum_j A_{ij})^2 + \varepsilon}$ with $\varepsilon = 10^{-8}$ (unitless; for softmax rows, $\text{sel} \approx [0, 1 - 1/N]$, lower \Rightarrow more peaked attention per query row).
- **Perturbation Robustness:** following [5], we measure the change in attention under additive input noise as $\Delta A = \|A(x) - A(x + \delta)\|_F$, where A and A' denote the post-softmax attention maps for the clean and perturbed inputs, respectively. We use i.i.d. Gaussian noise of magnitude $\epsilon_{\text{noise}} = 10^{-2}$ (clipped to $[0, 1]$). (unitless; $\Delta A \geq 0$, lower \Rightarrow greater attention-map stability).

We average each indicator over heads within a layer and then over layers (and over batch where applicable). The diagonal spectral parameters are initialized as $\sigma \sim \mathcal{N}(1.0, 0.1^2)$ per head and learned jointly with the rest of the model. Each σ_i is a trainable parameter updated by standard backpropagation (Adam) together with the ViT weights; interpretability is promoted via the ℓ_2 normalization of Q , K , orthogonality regularization on W^Q, W^K , and the spectral-entropy regularizer on Σ (Sec. IV).

V. RESULTS

We evaluated the interpretability and structural behavior of SVDA-based Vision Transformers using the six attention indicators across all layers and heads. Each indicator provides insight into a distinct aspect of the attention mechanism's structure, stability, and informativeness.

A. ACCURACY AND TRAINING TIME COMPARISON

To assess the computational implications of SVDA, we compared its accuracy and runtime against the baseline Vision Transformer across all datasets. TABLE 1 summarizes trainable parameters and theoretical compute (MACs) for a single forward pass. Let N be the number of tokens per image (including [CLS]) and d_k the per-head dimension. Standard self-attention computes scores QK^\top and outputs AV , each costing $\mathcal{O}(N^2 d_k)$ per head, with attention-map storage $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$. SVDA replaces the score kernel with $(Q\Sigma)K^\top$ where Σ is diagonal: the additional modulation $Q\Sigma$ and the row-wise ℓ_2 normalization of Q, K cost $\mathcal{O}(Nd_k)$ per head, while the dominant score and value products remain $\mathcal{O}(N^2 d_k)$ and memory remains $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$. Thus, SVDA preserves the asymptotic complexity of standard attention, with the trade-off primarily reflected in constant-factor overhead and implementation-level runtime/memory behavior (TABLE 1 and TABLE 2).

FIGURE 2. Validation accuracy (%) over epochs for baseline and SVDA models across datasets, shown as mean \pm standard deviation over three seeds. The two models exhibit broadly similar learning trajectories.

FIGURE 3. Training time per epoch (seconds) for baseline and SVDA models across datasets, shown as mean \pm standard deviation over three seeds. SVDA introduces a consistent but moderate runtime overhead due to its additional normalization and spectral modulation steps.

TABLE 1. Trainable parameters and MACs (single forward pass) for baseline vs. SVDA ViTs across datasets.

Dataset	Params (Base/SVDA)	MACs (Base/SVDA)
FashionMNIST	3,166,730 / 3,167,754	163.69 / 163.64 M
CIFAR-10	3,174,922 / 3,175,946	215.33 / 215.26 M
CIFAR-100	3,198,052 / 3,199,076	215.35 / 215.29 M
ImageNet-100	923,236 / 924,004	1.68 / 1.68 G

TABLE 2. Measured inference cost (CUDA), aggregated over three seeds: latency in ms per forward pass (mean), and peak allocated GPU memory in MiB (mean).

Dataset	Batch	Latency (Base/SVDA)	Peak Mem (Base/SVDA)
FashionMNIST	1	1.832 / 2.580	117.4 / 143.0
FashionMNIST	64	2.829 / 3.400	356.8 / 404.2
CIFAR-10	1	1.823 / 2.582	118.8 / 145.2
CIFAR-10	64	3.521 / 4.094	427.7 / 483.7
CIFAR-100	1	1.868 / 2.619	119.5 / 146.1
CIFAR-100	64	3.571 / 4.031	428.5 / 484.7
ImageNet-100	1	3.420 / 4.869	123.9 / 250.5
ImageNet-100	64	46.699 / 60.672	5394.2 / 5841.3

To separate training-time overhead from inference-time cost, we additionally profiled inference for both baseline and SVDA models under the same CUDA runtime environment. TABLE 2 reports seed-aggregated per-batch forward-pass latency (mean over three seeds) and mean peak allocated GPU memory.

FIGURE 2 shows that classification accuracy evolves similarly for both models throughout training. While both compared architectures maintain comparative and high validation accuracy on simpler datasets, such as FashionMNIST and CIFAR-10, we observe a pronounced generalization gap in CIFAR-100 and ImageNet-100, where training accuracy

exceeds 90% but validation accuracy plateaus below 50%. This overfitting behavior can be attributed to the limited capacity of the experimental architectures used—4 transformer layers with 4 heads (or 8 layers with 2 heads)—which are significantly shallower than standard Vision Transformers designed for high-resolution, high-diversity datasets. For example, ViT-Base employs 12 layers and 12 heads with a hidden size of 768 and is typically pretrained on massive datasets like JFT-300M before fine-tuning on ImageNet [1]. In contrast, our models are trained from scratch on modest-size datasets, which have been shown to be critical for generalization in transformer-based vision models [16], [17]. Furthermore, transformers are known to require substantial depth and width to disentangle fine-grained classes effectively, particularly in datasets like CIFAR-100 and ImageNet, which exhibit high intra-class variation and inter-class similarity [18]. These findings highlight both the limitations of compact transformer architectures and the need for capacity-aware interpretability analysis, as SVDA continues to reveal distinct structural properties even under suboptimal generalization.

Aggregated multi-seed results further clarify the classification picture in the compact from-scratch regime. On FashionMNIST and CIFAR-10, SVDA slightly exceeds the baseline in best validation accuracy, reaching approximately 87.79% versus 86.71% and 71.13% versus 70.65%, respectively. On the more challenging CIFAR-100 and ImageNet-100 benchmarks, SVDA remains competitive but somewhat lower, reaching approximately 38.63% versus 41.10% and 45.33% versus 47.02%, respectively. These results are consistent with our intended positioning of SVDA as an interpretability-oriented reformulation of attention rather than an accuracy-

maximization mechanism.

FIGURE 3 provides insight on the training time per epoch, showing a consistently higher trend for SVDA. This overhead stems primarily from the additional matrix normalization and spectral modulation operations introduced in the attention layers. Notably, the interpretability benefits of SVDA are achieved without compromising predictive performance, albeit with a modest computational cost. While SVDA introduces only minimal architectural overhead, adding fewer than 0.04% more trainable parameters in all cases, it consistently incurs a moderate training-time slowdown across datasets. Using the three-seed run summaries, the mean epoch time increases from approximately 12.94s to 15.77s on FashionMNIST, from 19.77s to 21.99s on CIFAR-10, from 20.24s to 22.54s on CIFAR-100, and from 594.21s to 650.18s on ImageNet-100. This corresponds to relative slowdowns of approximately 21.9%, 11.3%, 11.4%, and 9.4%, respectively, with an average slowdown of about 13.5% across the four datasets. This moderate increase in wall-clock time occurs despite similar (and sometimes slightly lower) theoretical Multiply-Accumulate Operations (MACs) per forward pass for SVDA (TABLE 1). However, MACs quantify arithmetic workload and do not necessarily predict hardware runtime; TABLE 2 shows that SVDA can incur higher measured latency and peak memory at inference even when MAC counts are comparable. For instance, on ImageNet-100, the two models have nearly identical MAC counts (1.68 GMACs), yet the seed-aggregated inference latency increases from approximately 46.70 ms to 60.67 ms at batch size 64, while mean peak memory rises from approximately 5394.2 MiB to 5841.3 MiB. This mismatch between theoretical computation and realized runtime is likely attributable to implementation-level inefficiencies. SVDA introduces additional normalization and spectral modulation operations, which may reduce kernel fusion opportunities and increase memory traffic compared to the baseline attention path. In contrast, baseline attention implementations benefit from mature, low-level CUDA kernels and fused operations available in modern deep learning frameworks such as PyTorch, in which we relied. Recent studies on efficient attention variants (e.g., [19]) emphasize that raw FLOP or MAC counts do not always translate linearly to performance on hardware accelerators, particularly when kernel fusion, memory layout, and parallelization are involved.

Thus, while SVDA incurs an average training slowdown of about 13.5% across datasets in the aggregated three-seed analysis, this cost is relatively modest given the structural interpretability and spectral regularization benefits it provides. Future versions may reduce this gap through custom kernel optimization and batching strategies that better exploit GPU hardware.

B. VALIDATION IN A PRETRAINED FINE-TUNING REGIME

To assess whether the conclusions extend beyond compact from-scratch training, we additionally evaluated SVDA in a

standard pretrained fine-tuning setting based on a pretrained ViT backbone on ImageNet-100. Rather than replacing all pretrained attention blocks, we integrated the exact SVDA operator into the final two transformer blocks, while preserving the earlier pretrained blocks unchanged. This design allows us to test SVDA in a realistic pretrained regime without disrupting the full pretrained representation hierarchy.

Across three seeds, the pretrained baseline achieved a best accuracy of approximately 90.5%, while the late-block SVDA variant achieved approximately 88.5%. The corresponding final accuracies were approximately 90.2% and 88.3%, respectively. Measured runtime overhead remained modest: mean epoch time increased from approximately 215.9s to 258.5s, while trainable parameter counts remained nearly unchanged (1,095,076 for the baseline versus 1,095,460 for the SVDA variant). To assess whether the learned attention remains relevant to the model's predictions, we additionally performed deletion/insertion-based faithfulness evaluation on the pretrained models: top-attended image patches were either removed or progressively restored and compared against random patch selections. In this setting, the pretrained SVDA model retained prediction-relevant attention behavior, with particularly strong deletion-based relevance at larger masking fractions. For example, at 20% masking the deletion score increased from approximately 0.208 for the pretrained baseline to 0.227 for the SVDA variant, and at 30% masking it increased from approximately 0.343 to 0.369. These results indicate that SVDA is not limited to compact from-scratch training and can also remain viable when integrated into a standard pretrained/fine-tuned ViT pipeline.

C. METRIC EVOLUTION AND LAYERWISE ANALYSIS

FIGURE 4 and FIGURE 5 present the trajectories of interpretability indicators across training epochs, along with boxplot summaries per transformer layer, for all datasets over 100 training epochs.

Temporal evolution. Across all datasets, spectral entropy exhibits a consistent downward trend, indicating that the attention spectra become increasingly compact over time. This reflects an emergent concentration of energy in fewer spectral components, aligned with our interpretability objectives. Effective rank similarly decreases, supporting the formation of low-rank attention maps. In contrast, angular alignment increases steadily during training, indicating stronger directional coherence between queries and keys—a marker of improved semantic alignment in the attention structure.

The selectivity index remains high (near 1) with a mild downward drift, suggesting stable but slightly more distributed attention allocation. Spectral sparsity initially rises, then stabilizes into a noisy low-level plateau after approximately 50 epochs (values between 0.04 and 0.1), indicating that only a small fraction of spectral entries is suppressed. Perturbation robustness (measured as ΔA) remains very small (on the order of 10^{-8} – 10^{-7}) and shows a mild up-

FIGURE 4. SVDA interpretability and structural attention diagnostics across datasets and interpretability indicators (part 1 of 2): (a) Spectral Entropy evolution per epoch; (b) Spectral Entropy per layer; (c) Effective Rank evolution per epoch; (d) Effective Rank per layer; (e) Angular Alignment evolution per epoch; (f) Angular Alignment per layer.

FIGURE 5. SVDA interpretability and structural attention diagnostics across datasets and interpretability indicators (part 2 of 2): (g) Selectivity Index evolution per epoch; (h) Selectivity Index per layer; (i) Spectral Sparsity evolution per epoch; (j) Spectral Sparsity per layer; (k) Perturbation Robustness evolution per epoch; (l) Perturbation Robustness per layer.

ward drift across epochs, suggesting that attention maps stay largely stable under additive input noise in our setting, with no consistent improvement over training.

Layerwise behavior. Boxplot analyses across layers reveal substantial variation. For spectral entropy and effective rank, early layers tend to show broader interquartile ranges, while deeper layers converge toward tighter, more stable medians. Angular alignment and perturbation robustness exhibit pronounced median shifts across layers, suggesting hierarchical differentiation in attention structure. The selectivity index remains consistently high across layers, though its spread varies, indicating the coexistence of highly focused and more diffusely distributed heads within each layer.

Overall, this dual-axis analysis—temporal and structural—demonstrates that SVDA fosters not only interpretable attention dynamics over time but also distinctive attention behaviors across layers. These traits enhance model transparency while preserving competitive predictive behavior in our experimental settings.

Within our compact-from-scratch experimental setting, SVDA-based models closely track the baseline’s classification accuracy across the considered datasets, while offering markedly improved structural diagnostics of attention behavior. The six diagnostic metrics jointly reveal that SVDA promotes a spectrum-aware and geometrically grounded attention mechanism.

These diagnostics remain informative on the more challenging CIFAR-100 and ImageNet-100 settings. We interpret the indicator trends as evidence of measurable structural behavior in our controlled compact-model setting.

Deletion/insertion-based faithfulness evaluation provides complementary evidence that the learned SVDA attention is prediction-relevant rather than merely structurally organized. In particular, SVDA shows stronger deletion-based relevance on the more challenging datasets. On CIFAR-10, the deletion score at 20% masking increases from approximately 0.167 for the baseline to 0.198 for SVDA. On CIFAR-100, the corresponding 30% masking score increases from approximately 0.377 to 0.443, and on ImageNet-100 from approximately 0.517 to 0.583. These results indicate that, especially in the harder settings, the most attended regions identified by SVDA are more tightly coupled to the final prediction under perturbation-based testing.

D. QUALITATIVE VISUAL-REGION CONSISTENCY

Qualitative overlays on ImageNet-100 provide complementary visual evidence that SVDA tends to focus more clearly on target-relevant image regions. In the representative examples of FIGURE 6, baseline attention is often more spatially diffuse, whereas SVDA yields sharper and more spatially organized responses concentrated around salient object regions and contours. This qualitative behavior is consistent with the quantitative faithfulness-based evaluation and supports the view that SVDA attention is more closely aligned with image regions that support the final prediction.

A code repository is available at https://github.com/VasilisTz1/svda_image_classification.

VI. DISCUSSION

The empirical results across the four from-scratch datasets and the additional pretrained fine-tuning study support a consistent overall interpretation of SVDA. The proposed attention operator does not aim to outperform standard ViT attention in raw classification accuracy; rather, its purpose is to impose a more structured and diagnostically accessible attention mechanism while preserving competitive predictive behavior. In this sense, the most relevant outcome of the study is not a uniform accuracy gain, but the observation that SVDA repeatedly produces attention patterns that can be analyzed through a coherent family of structural and faithfulness-oriented indicators without incurring meaningful parameter growth.

This distinction is important for interpreting the results correctly. The six SVDA indicators are descriptive rather than prescriptive: they are intended to characterize spectral concentration, alignment, selectivity, sparsity, and robustness of the learned attention patterns, not to serve as direct surrogates for task performance. Accordingly, the paper should not be read as claiming that structurally sharper or spectrally more compact attention necessarily yields higher classification accuracy in every setting. At the same time, the present study is not purely post-hoc: the entropy-related regularization term already injects one indicator-linked training signal into the optimization objective, while the added deletion/insertion experiments evaluate whether the resulting attention patterns remain prediction-relevant. Instead, the evidence suggests that SVDA provides a useful interpretability-oriented bias, making the internal behavior of attention easier to quantify and compare across datasets, layers, and training regimes.

The from-scratch experiments show that this descriptive value is not confined to a single benchmark. Across FashionMNIST, CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and ImageNet-100, the indicator trajectories reveal stable and non-trivial structure in the learned attention, while the added deletion/insertion-based faithfulness evaluation shows that highly attended regions are not arbitrary: they are meaningfully connected to the model’s predictions. This combination is important because structural metrics alone do not establish explanation quality. The deletion/insertion results therefore strengthen the interpretation of the indicators by showing that the attended regions identified by SVDA remain prediction-relevant under perturbation-based testing.

The additional pretrained fine-tuning experiment further broadens the scope of the study. Rather than replacing attention throughout the entire pretrained backbone, we used late-block integration of the exact SVDA operator in a standard pretrained ViT pipeline on ImageNet-100. This choice preserves the earlier pretrained representation hierarchy while testing whether SVDA remains viable in a more practical and standardized setting. The resulting late-block SVDA model remains competitive with the pretrained

FIGURE 6. Representative qualitative attention overlays on ImageNet-100. In each example, the left panel shows the input image, the middle panel the baseline attention overlay, and the right panel the SVDA attention overlay.

baseline, while preserving meaningful prediction-relevant attention behavior and only modest runtime overhead. More specifically, the deletion/insertion analysis in the pretrained setting evaluates whether the regions emphasized by attention are genuinely related to the model's decision: top-attended patches are either removed or progressively restored and the resulting confidence changes are compared against random patch selections. Under this test, the pretrained SVDA variant showed particularly strong deletion-based relevance at larger masking fractions, with the deletion score increasing from approximately 0.208 to 0.227 at 20% masking and from approximately 0.343 to 0.369 at 30% masking relative to the pretrained baseline. This indicates that the most attended regions remained substantially tied to the final prediction. We view this as evidence that SVDA is not confined to compact from-scratch architectures, although the strongest and most comprehensive empirical support in the present paper still comes from the controlled compact-model regime.

These observations suggest several concrete directions for future work. A natural next step is to extend the pretrained analysis to larger backbones and broader fine-tuning settings, including full end-to-end integration under matched optimization protocols. It is also important to study whether subsets of the SVDA indicators can be turned into lightweight auxiliary objectives that encourage specific structural regimes without undermining task performance. Finally, the same framework could be explored in other Transformer-based vision tasks, such as dense prediction, segmentation, or multimodal fusion, where structured and interpretable attention may be even more valuable. More broadly, SVDA provides a path toward attention mechanisms whose internal behavior is easier to inspect, quantify, and reason about, which is a central requirement for transparent and trustworthy deep learning systems.

VII. CONCLUSION

We have presented Spectral-Value-Decomposed Attention (SVDA), a geometrically grounded reformulation of self-attention designed to enhance the interpretability and structure of attention mechanisms in Vision Transformers. By combining l_2 -normalized query/key projections with a learned diagonal spectral modulation matrix, SVDA imposes an explicit separation between directional alignment and spectral importance, leading to more focused and semantically organized attention maps.

Empirical results across four benchmark datasets—FashionMNIST, CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and ImageNet-100—demonstrate that SVDA preserves competitive classi-

fication behavior while providing substantially richer interpretability diagnostics. This is quantified through six descriptive indicators: spectral entropy, effective rank, spectral sparsity, angular alignment, selectivity index, and perturbation robustness. Together with the added deletion/insertion analysis, these measurements show that SVDA yields attention patterns that are both structurally organized and meaningfully connected to the model's predictions.

SVDA is architecture-compatible with ViT blocks and, within our compact-from-scratch setting, embeds intrinsic interpretability diagnostics while preserving competitive predictive behavior. In addition to the compact from-scratch experiments, we also showed that SVDA can be integrated into a standard pretrained/fine-tuned ViT regime through late-block replacement on ImageNet-100, providing stronger practical validation beyond the original compact setting. Future work will investigate broader pretrained configurations, larger backbones, full end-to-end SVDA integration, and simple auxiliary regularizers that target specific indicators under matched protocols.

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